

Phthaleins and Rhodamines Derived from Furan-2,3,4,5-Tetracarboxylic Acid. Effect of Replacing the Benzene Ring by a Furan Ring

S. D. Loiwai and N. C. Jain

Furan-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxylic acid has been condensed with a number of hydroxy- and hydroxyamino-aromatic compounds to study the effect of introducing a furan ring in phthaleins and rhodamines. Replacement of the benzene ring by a furan ring has no appreciable effect on the wave length of maximum absorption except in the case of phenol, *o*-cresol, *m*-diethylaminophenol, and octabromoresorcinol derivatives.

After studying the effect of introducing various substituted and partly saturated benzene rings¹ and also of a thiophene ring² in phthaleins and rhodamines, it was also thought desirable to study the effect of a furan ring in phthalein and rhodamine dyes. With this aim, furan-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxylic acid (IV) was prepared, starting from ethyl oxalato *via* sodio-oxaloacetic ester (I)³ and dioxalosuccinic ester (II or IIA)⁴. The latter was cyclised to furan tetracarboxylic ester (III)⁵, which on hydrolysis yielded furan-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxylic acid (IV)⁵.

1. Loiwai and Jain, *this Journal*, 1962, **39**, 251, 385, 745; 1963, **40**, 680.

2. *Idem*, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1963, **1**, 119.

3. Cohen, "Practical Organic Chemistry", Macmillan & Co. Ltd., London, 1940, p. 126.

4. Sutter, *Annalen*, 1932, **499**, 47.

5. Reichstein *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1933, **16**, 276.

The acid (IV) has been condensed with resorcinol, orcinol, phloroglucinol, pyrogallol, phenol, *o*-cresol, and *m*-diethyleminophenol to obtain various phthaleins and rhodamines (Types A & B).

Type A.

- V : $R^1=R^2=R^4=H$; $R^3=-OH$.
- VI : $R^1=Me$; $R^2=R^4=H$; $R^3=-OH$.
- VII : $R^2=R^3=-OH$; $R^1=R^4=H$.
- VIII : $R^1=R^2=H$; $R^3=R^4=-OH$.
- IX : $R^1=R^2=R^4=H$; $R^3=-NEt_2$.
- X : $R^1=H$; $R^2=R^4=Br$; $R^3=-OH$.
- XI : $R^1=R^2=R^4=H$; $R^3=-OCOMe$.

Type B.

- XII : $R^1=-OH$; $R^2=H$.
- XIII : $R^1=-OH$; $R^2=Me$.

The fluorescent phthalein, obtained from resorcinol, has also been brominated and acetylated. The absorption characteristics of these dyes have been studied spectrophotometrically, using "Hilger Uvispek" spectrophotometer, in order to study the effect of the furan nucleus on the absorption maxima of the various phthaleins. Table II records a comparative study of the absorptions of the two series (phthaleins and rhodamines from phthalic acid and those from furan-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxylic acid).

The absorption maxima of the phloroglucinol compound (VII) could not be determined due to fading of the colour on adding alkali to the ethanolic solution.

Furan-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxyleins could have three possible structures.

Structures (a) and (b) are rather doubtful due to steric hindrance. Structure (c) has therefore been incorporated in the paper as the possible structure for the phthaleins and rhodamines from furan tetracarboxylic acid.

On comparing the absorption data of furan-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxyleins with those of phthaleins and rhodamines (from phthalic acid), it has been found that the replacement of a benzene ring by a furan ring has no appreciable effect in general. Slightly lower values in case of phenol, *o*-cresol, and *m*-diethylaminophenol compounds of furan-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxylic acid may be due to the lower values (λ_{max}) of furan as compared to the higher values of benzene (in the UV region). Furthermore, the fact that the octabromoresorcinolfuran-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxylein (X) absorbs at higher wave lengths than eosin may be accounted for by the presence of eight bromine atoms in the dye molecule, when compared to four in the case of eosin.

EXPERIMENTAL

Furan-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxylic acid (IV) was prepared, involving the following steps:

Sodio-oxaloacetic ester (I)³ was first prepared, starting from ethyl oxalate, sodium, and ethyl acetate. The ester (I) was then converted into dioxalosuccinic ester⁴ (II or IIA) by the action of bromine in chloroform. The ester (II), as formulated by Sutter⁴ or, (IIA) as formulated by Reichstein *et al.*⁵, on treatment with H_2SO_4 (conc.) yielded a cyclised tetracarboxylic ester (furan-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxylic ester, III)⁵. The ester (III) on hydrolysis with HCl (conc.) and glacial acetic acid afforded the required furan tetracarboxylic acid (IV). The acid (IV) after crystallisation from acetonebenzene mixture melted at 247° (*ca.*) with decomposition.

The phthaleins and rhodamines, noted below, were then prepared, using acid (IV) by methods described earlier^{1,2}.

Resorcinolfuran-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxylein (V) was obtained by condensing the acid (IV) (2.44 g.) with resorcinol (5.0 g.) at 160-80° for 3 hr. in presence of 3 to 4 drops of H_2SO_4 (conc.).

Orcinolfuran-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxylein (VI) was obtained like the compound (V) from a mixture of the acid (IV) (0.61 g.) and orcinol (1.25 g.) by heating at 180-200° for 3 hr. in presence of a few drops of H_2SO_4 (conc.).

Phloroglucinolfuran-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxylein (VII) was obtained like the compound (V) by heating a mixture of the acid (IV) (1.22 g.) and phloroglucinol (2.75 g.) under identical conditions.

Pyrogallolfuran-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxylein (VIII) was obtained from a mixture of the acid (IV, 1.22 g.) and pyrogallol (2.75 g.) by condensation under conditions similar to compound (VII).

m-*Diethylaminophenolfuran-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxylein* (IX) was obtained by condensation of a mixture of the acid (IV, 1.22 g.), *m*-diethylaminophenol (3.35 g.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 3 or 4 drops) at 140-50° for 4 hr.

Octabromoresorcinolfuran-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxylein (X) was prepared by brominating the resorcinolphthalein (V) by the method of Baeyer⁶.

Resorcinolfuran-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxylein tetra-acetate (XI) was obtained by acetylating compound (V) with acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate.

Phenolfuran-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxylein (XII) was obtained by heating a mixture of the acid (IV, 2.44 g.) and excess of phenol (4.5 g.) at 110-15° for 14 hr. in presence of a few drops of H₂SO₄ (conc.). The excess of phenol was removed by steam distillation and compound (XII) purified by methods described earlier¹⁻².

o-Cresolfuran-2,3,4,5-tetracarboxylein (XIII) was obtained like compound (XII) from a mixture of the acid (IV, 2.44 g.) and *o*-cresol (5.0 g.) by heating at 115-20° for 14 hr.

The characteristic properties and analytical data of the above compounds are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Dyes.	M.P.**	Colour of crystals.	Colour in		Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
			EtOH soln.	Alk.-EtOH soln.			
V	260°	Dark red	Orange*	Pink*	C ₃₂ H ₁₆ O ₁₁	C : 66.40% H : 2.79	66.56 2.77
VI	> 300°	Dark brown	Yellow*	Orange-yellow*	C ₃₆ H ₂₄ O ₁₁	C : 68.20 H : 3.80	68.35 3.79
VII	> 300°	Brown	Orange	Blood-red	C ₃₂ H ₁₆ O ₁₃	C : 59.80 H : 2.52	60.00 2.50
VIII	> 300°	Black	Light pink	Dirty pinkish green	C ₃₂ H ₁₆ O ₁₃	C : 59.85 H : 2.48	60.00 2.50
IX	206°	Dark pink	Pink	Purple-pink†	C ₄₈ H ₃₀ O ₇ N ₄	C : 72.12 H : 6.56 N : 7.00	72.36 6.53 7.03
X	152°	Pink-red	„	Pink	C ₃₂ H ₈ O ₁₁ Br ₈	Br : 52.80	52.98
XI	215°	Light brown	Brownish	..	C ₄₀ H ₂₄ O ₁₃	C : 64.40 H : 3.20	64.51 3.22
XII	155°	Pinkish white	Light yellow	Pink	C ₃₂ H ₂₀ O ₉	C : 69.85 H : 3.68	70.07 3.65
XIII	242°	„	Very light yellow	Purple-pink	C ₃₆ H ₂₈ O ₉	C : 71.30 H : 4.85	71.52 4.69

*With green fluorescence.

†Acidic EtOH solution.

**With decomposition.

TABLE II

Phenols.	$\lambda_{\max}$		$\lambda_{\max}^*$ for furan-2,3,4,5 tetracarboxyleins.	
	Neutral.	Alkaline.	Neutral.	Alkaline.
Phthalein dyes.				
Resorcinol	450 m μ	490 m μ	470 m μ	490 m μ
Orcinol	445	490	490	495
Phloroglucinol	440	460	..	..
Pyrogallol	..	..	..	535
Octabromoresorcinol	525	515	545	545
	(eosin)		(eosin)	
Phenol	..	545	..	525
o-Cresol	..	560	..	535
Rhodamine dyes.				
m-Diethylaminophenol	535	545	530	535

*The absorption maxima ($\lambda_{\max}$) of all the dyes were taken in ethanol with addition of a drop of 5% NaOH (in case of phthaleins) and a few drops of 5N-HCl (in case of rhodamines).

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